

SiC-CuSnSi COMPOSITES BY PRESSURELESS MELT INFILTRATION

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SUMMARY: The influence of tin and titanium as alloying elements of copper on the reactions and the wetting behaviour of a copper melt with SiC was investigated using sessile-drop-experiments. Titanium reacts with SiC forming wettable reaction zones and thereby allows the spreading of the melt on the ceramic. Tin as an alloying element leads to a clear reduction of the reactivity with SiC and to an improvement of the wetting behaviour at constant titanium concentrations.

The good wetting behaviour of the tin bronze containing titanium facilitates the pressureless melt infiltration of bronze in titanium activated SiC preforms. The titanium, homogeneously distributed as a metal powder in the preform, dissolves in the melt and reacts with SiC to form wettable TiC interfaces. With a bending strength of 324 MPa and a fracture toughness of 5,9 MPa m^{1/2} the best mechanical properties were shown by a composite produced by the melt infiltration of a Cu88Sn12-alloy in a preform of composition SiC84Ti16.

KEYWORDS: infiltration, wetting, sessile-drop, CuSn, SiC, interfaces, Ti-activation, TiC

INTRODUCTION

Due to the high hardness, corrosion resistance and good thermal conductivity SiC ceramics are used in wear-protection technology. Brittle behaviour and a susceptibility to unexpected catastrophic failure, however, limits the use of SiC under impact loading or high cyclic mechanical stress, as for example in bearings and linings of extruders and mills. The development of damage tolerant, corrosion resistant SiC-metal composites may extend the application range of materials based on SiC.

One fabrication method for such composites is pressureless, capillary driven infiltration of a metallic melt into a porous SiC matrix. Melt infiltration is an economical near-net-shape process for the production of dense materials. An inherent difficulty which limits the use of this technique is that many molten metals as for example Al, Co, Cu, Fe and Ni show poor wetting on SiC and react with SiC to form silicides and free carbon or carbides and free silicon.

In the first part of the paper using sessile-drop experiments it is shown how Cu/SiC reactions can be controlled by using tin as an alloying element and how titanium as an active element can facilitate the wetting on SiC. In the second part the results are transferred to the production of CuSnSi/SiC composites by melt infiltration.

REACTIVITY AND WETTING BEHAVIOUR OF CuSn WITH SiC

The reaction of a copper melt with SiC leads to a decomposition of the ceramic and dissolution of silicon in the melt until the equilibrium concentration of Si in the melt is reached. This concentration depends on the interactions of the dissolved silicon with the various elements in the melt. A measure of the intensity of this interaction is the partial enthalpy of mixing at infinite dilution of silicon in the melt [1]. By the addition of alloying elements like Sn, Zn or Pb with weaker interactions and thereby more positive partial mixing enthalpies with dissolved silicon [2], a reduction of the silicon equilibrium concentration in the melt and thereby a control of the metal-ceramic reactions should be possible.

The reactivity of Cu and CuSn-alloys with 15 and 25 wt.% Sn on polycrystalline SiC was investigated using sessile-drop experiments. The pure etched metals were placed in the appropriate weight ratio on polished SiC substrates in a SiSiC tube heated externally. The alloy with a total weight of 1,5 g was formed in-situ. The sessile-drop-experiments were carried out at 1150°C and hold times between 1 and 15 h in argon, the heating and cooling rate was 10 K/min. During the experiment, the contact area between melt and substrate was recorded by a video camera and the contact angle was determined. After cooling, samples with cross sections perpendicular to the interfaces were prepared and the Si content in the solidified drops which separated from the substrates on cooling was measured using energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS).

At the interface between the metallic melt and substrate, SiC is decomposed, leading to dissolution of silicon in the melt and the formation of a reaction zone of carbon precipitated in a CuSnSi matrix. The surface of the reaction zone is in the plane of the SiC substrate. Fig. 1 shows a vertical cut through the reaction zones formed by the reaction of Cu and a Cu75Sn25-alloy on SiC with a hold time of 15 h. In Fig. 2 the measured silicon concentrations in the solidified drops after hold times of 1, 3, 6, 9 and 15 h are shown.

Fig. 1: Reaction zones formed by the reaction of Cu and a Cu75Sn25-alloy on SiC with a hold time of 15h at 1150°C.

Fig. 2: Si-concentrations in the solidified drops as a function of the Cu content of the original alloys after hold times of 1, 3, 6, 9 and 15 h.

Tin as an alloying element of copper leads to a clear reduction of the reactivity with SiC. After a maximum hold time of 15 h the equilibrium state is reached.

Immediately after the melting of the alloy the wetting angle on the substrate was seen to be time independent, indicating the reaction zone was rapidly established. The measured wetting angles are shown in Table 1. Tin has no significant effect on the wetting behaviour of the melt.

Table 1: Wetting angle of CuSn-alloys on SiC substrates at 1150°C

alloy	Cu	Cu85Sn15	Cu75Sn25
wetting angle [°]	132 ± 3	138 ± 4	134 ± 4

REACTIVITY AND WETTING BEHAVIOUR OF CuSnTi WITH SiC

The driving force for a pressureless melt infiltration is the capillary pressure difference at the infiltration front. A pressureless infiltration is only possible in wettable metal ceramic systems and wetting angles well below 90° are necessary to overcome friction losses. It is known from the active brazing technology, that by adding titanium as an active alloying element in copper a wetting of Cu on SiC can be achieved [3]. A positive effect of tin on the wetting behaviour of CuSnTi-alloys was observed by Yupko [4] after hold times of 60 seconds.

The wetting behaviour of titanium activated Cu and CuSn-alloys with 10, 15 and 25 wt.% Sn and Ti concentrations between 0,2 and 4,0 wt.% was investigated by sessile-drop-experiments under vacuum (10^{-5} to 10^{-6} mbar) in a furnace with molybdenum lining. The hold time at 1150°C was 60 min. The weight of the alloy which was formed in-situ was reduced to 0,5 g.

The wetting angles in Table 2 which were measured at the end of the experiments, show that titanium leads to a wetting of the alloys on SiC. With increasing tin contents an improvement of the wetting behaviour results at constant titanium concentrations. An increase of the

titanium activity and a decrease of the surface tension of the melt by tin can explain this positive influence. Fig. 3 shows pictures of Cu- and CuSn-alloys with a titanium content of 1% after sessile-drop-experiments on SiC.

Table 2: Wetting angle of CuSnTi-alloys on SiC after 1h at 1150°C

Ti-content	0,2 %	0,5 %	1 %	2 %	3%	4 %
Cu	79	77	42	39	<10	<10
Cu90Sn10	26	<10	<10	<10	-----	<10
Cu85Sn15	21	<10	<10	<10	-----	<10
Cu75Sn25	16	<10	<10	<10	-----	<10

Fig. 3: Cu- and CuSn-alloys with a titanium content of 1% on SiC after 1h at 1150°C

At the interface alloy/substrate as well as the reaction zone from carbon precipitation in a CuSnSi-matrix titanium rich reaction zones are formed. Fig. 4 shows the reaction zones which were formed by the reaction of a (Cu90Sn10)96Ti4-alloy with SiC. On cooling the alloy separated from the substrate, the fracture went through the CuSnSi/C reaction zone. The titanium rich reaction zone, which is divided into two layers, consists of TiC in the lower part and of Ti_5Si_3 in the upper part. Fig. 5 shows the concentration profile in the titanium rich reaction zones of the sample shown in Fig. 4. The concentration profile was measured at the bottom of the sample by glow discharge optical emission spectrometry (GDOES) after grinding off the CuSnSi/C-reaction zone with abrasive paper. The high carbon concentrations at the beginning of the measurement can be explained by hydrocarbon adsorption at the interface after grinding.

Fig. 4: Reaction zones formed at the interface between a (Cu₉₀Sn₁₀)₉₆Ti₄-alloy and SiC after 1h at 1150°C

Fig. 5: Concentration profile in the Ti-rich reaction zones (measured at the bottom of the sample in Fig. 4 after grinding off the CuSnSi/C reaction zone)

In experiments with titanium activated Cu₉₃Si₇- and (Cu₈₅Sn₁₅)₉₇Si₃-alloys with a Si content above the Si equilibrium concentrations as determined from Fig. 2, a single reaction zone out of TiC was formed. The formation of the CuSnSi/C-reaction zone which results from the saturation of the melt with silicon was no longer observed. The absence of the Ti₅Si₃ reaction zone reveals that the formation of this zone in the experiments without pre-alloying with Si is favoured by high Si concentrations at the interface resulting from the SiC decomposition.

SiC-CuSnSi COMPOSITES WITH TAILORED TiC INTERFACES

To infiltrate CuSn alloys into SiC matrices without an applied pressure, a new process based on the good wetting behaviour of CuSnTi alloys on SiC was developed. SiC powder ($d_{V50} =$

27 μm) and Ti powder ($d_{V50} = 26 \mu\text{m}$) were mixed and homogeneous green bodies with a porosity of approximately 51 % and an average pore size of 7 μm fabricated by slip casting. Alloys with a Sn content between 0 and 15 wt.% which are either commercially available (Cu, G-Cu90Sn10 after DIN 1705) or were pre-prepared from the pure metals on BN-covered SiC are placed on these preforms. The infiltration process is performed at 1150°C for Cu and 1100°C for the bronze under vacuum (10^{-5} to 10^{-6} mbar) with hold times between 30 and 120 min.

The Ti in the preform dissolves in the melt, diffuses to the metal-ceramic interfaces and reacts with the SiC. Initially, the reaction of the melt with the SiC leads to a rapid decomposition of the SiC and thereby to an enrichment of the melt with Si. The Si-enriched melt then infiltrates the remainder of the preform as wettable TiC interfaces with a thickness of approximately 1 μm are formed. Fig. 6 shows a general view of the microstructure and a single SiC grain surrounded with a TiC interface in an etched CuSnSi-alloy after infiltration of Cu90Sn10 in a preform of composition SiC84Ti16.

Fig. 6: Cu90Sn10 infiltrated in SiC84Ti16

By adding silicon to the alloys it is possible to suppress the decomposition of the SiC in the initial stage. In infiltration experiments with a Cu95Si5-alloy no decomposition of the SiC particles was observed. The Si concentration necessary is therefore below the Si equilibrium concentration as determined from Fig. 2. Independent of the Si content in the original alloy the titanium reacts with SiC according to reaction (1)

(the elements in brackets are dissolved in the melt). This results in a continuous enrichment of the melt with silicon at the infiltration front. For a Ti content in the preform of 16 wt.% a Si-concentration in the melt of approximately 2 % results from this reaction.

The dependence of the infiltration behaviour on the Ti concentration was investigated by infiltration experiments with Cu and Cu90Sn10 in preforms with Ti contents between 8 and 24 wt.% and a hold time of 30 min. Fig. 7 shows the measured open porosity as a function of the Ti content in the preforms.

Fig. 7: Open porosity as a function of the Ti-content in the preforms

The open porosity decreases and the density of the infiltrated samples increases with an increasing Ti content in the preforms. For both metals, composites with an open porosity below 1 % could be produced. For Cu the necessary Ti content in the preform to achieve this was 20 %, whereas a Ti content of 16 % was sufficient in the case of the Cu90Sn10 alloy. This can be related to the specific surface area of the SiC (0,19 m²/g determined by BET-measurements) and corresponds to a titanium concentration per m²-SiC of 1,3 g/m² for Cu and 1,0 g/m² for the Cu90Sn10-alloy. So, the infiltration behaviour reflects the better wetting behaviour of CuSnTi-alloys on SiC with increasing Sn content as observed in sessile-drop-experiments, showing a good correlation between the "model" interfaces and "real" composites.

For a characterisation of the mechanical properties, composites with the dimensions 60x28x8 mm were produced by melt infiltration with a hold time of 1h. The bending strength was measured by 4-point bending tests according to EN 843-1, the fracture toughness was determined by 4-point bending tests with the SEVNB-method (Single Edge V-Notched Beam [5]). The test samples with dimensions of 2x2,5x25 mm were cut out of the lower part of the

composites by wire erosion. A further surface treatment was not carried out. The measurements were done at room temperature.

In Table 3 the measured bending strength and fracture toughness are shown, the values are an average of 5 measurements. Fig. 8 shows the fracture surface and etched microstructure for a composite that was produced by melt infiltration of a Cu85Sn15 alloy in a SiC84Ti16 preform. Assuming a complete reaction of the titanium in the preform with SiC during the formation of a wettable $TiC_{0,6}$ phase, the volume percentage of carbides (SiC+TiC) in the composites is 44 %. The TiC volume in the composites increases from 6 % for the Cu84Ti16 preform to 10 % for the Cu76Ti24 preform.

Table 3: Flexural strength and fracture toughness, measured by 4-point bending tests

infiltrated alloy	preform	flexural strength (MPa)	fracture toughness K_{Ic} (MPa m ^{1/2})
Cu	SiC76Ti24	----	4,00 ± 0,02
Cu	SiC80Ti20	216 ± 16	4,38 ± 0,58
Cu90Sn10	SiC84Ti16	180 ± 30	3,63 ± 0,13
Cu88Sn12	SiC76Ti24	272 ± 30	5,25 ± 0,10
Cu88Sn12	SiC84Ti16	324 ± 16	5,90 ± 0,12
Cu85Sn15	SiC84Ti16	268 ± 30	4,90 ± 0,23

Fig. 8: Fracture surface and etched microstructure for a composite that was produced by melt infiltration of a Cu85Sn15 alloy in a SiC84Ti16 preform

Principal differences in the fracture behaviour of the investigated composites could not be ascertained, in all cases the fracture passed through the SiC particles. The fracture behaviour is determined by the high percentage of hard, brittle phases, which prevent a ductile deformation of the whole sample. Beside the ceramic reinforcement SiC/TiC the composites consist of a mixture of brittle and ductile phases. For the copper infiltrated composites the matrix consist of Cu₅Si and Cu₇Si. For composites infiltrated with the tin bronze the ductile α -phase and the hard δ -phase of the binary CuSn-system and coppersilicides have been identified by XRD.

CONCLUSION

The requirements for the production of metal/ceramic-composites by melt infiltration are a control of the reactions and a wetting of the ceramic by the melt. Using sessile-drop experiments it has been shown that the reactivity of Cu with SiC can be controlled by tin additions and good wetting of tin bronze with wetting angles below 10° on SiC can be achieved by using Ti as reactive element.

Using this information to tailor SiC/metal interfaces dense, particle reinforced CuSnSi/SiC composites with a bending strength up to 324 MPa and fracture toughness up to 5,9 MPa m^{1/2} have been produced by a new process. An activation of the preforms with titanium leads to a continuous Ti enrichment of the melt during the infiltration process. The Ti dissolved in the melt reacts with SiC forming a wettable TiC interface and thereby allows the pressureless infiltration. The mechanical properties show the potential of these new materials to replace SSiC and SiSiC for critical wear applications.

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